

DEVELOPMENT OF A NOVEL HALL EFFECT SENSOR TO MONITOR THE
THICKNESS OF A CURING COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

An in-situ thickness/compaction sensor has been developed based on the Hall effect. The basic Hall sensor is a transducer that will produce an output voltage when subjected to changes in an applied magnetic field. The output voltage of the sensor is empirically related to the distance between the sensor, located on the tooling surface, and a magnet mounted to the caul plate. The sensor is small and unobtrusive and its cost is low. The accuracy of the sensor is approximately ± 0.003 inches over the range of 0.090 to 0.250 inches. The results of this research show that the sensor can be successfully used for on-line monitoring of thickness and compaction of a curing composite.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are few sensors capable of directly measuring the chemical and physical changes that occur in a thermoset or a thermoplastic composite while being processed in a mold, press, or autoclave [1,2]. Increased emphasis on the development of sensors and empirical relationships to correlate the sensor output to the chemical and physical properties of the laminate is desired to improve efficiency and reliability in the processing environment. At the present time the attractiveness of composite properties are outweighed by the labor intensive nature of the manufacturing environment. With additional on-line process control research and sensor development this problem can be eliminated.

The availability of an in-situ thickness sensor will allow errors in the process cycle and equipment malfunctions (process aberrations) to be corrected or compensated for while the part is being prepared, resulting in a savings of time and money. The final part thickness of a composite material affects the fiber content which is related to the mechanical and physical properties. In-situ sensing of dimensional changes will allow the control of composite compaction and final thickness, thus ensuring the part will meet specified properties and dimensional tolerances.

The basic Hall sensor is essentially a transducer that will generate a voltage if an applied magnetic field changes in any manner. Linear Hall-effect sensors are ratiometric, i.e., they have an output proportional to

the magnetic field applied to the 'active area' of the sensor. The output of a linear Hall-effect sensor can then be empirically related to the distance between the magnet and the sensor.

The objectives of this work were to develop an in-situ sensor based on the Hall effect to monitor the thickness of a curing composite material, to establish its sensitivity, and to study the effects of processing environment on the performance of the sensor.

2. DEVELOPMENTAL WORK

2.1 Background

A magnetic field applied to a conductor carrying current produces a voltage across the conductor [3]. The effect is caused by electron deflection within the solid, concentrating the negative charges at one side or the other depending on the influence of the magnetic field lines. The difference in potential is called the Hall voltage.

The output null voltage of the Hall sensor is nominally one-half the supply voltage. A south magnetic pole presented to the branded face of the Hall effect sensor will drive the output higher than the null voltage level. A north magnetic pole will drive the output below the null voltage level. If the biased Hall sensor is placed in a magnetic field with the flux lines at right angles to the Hall current, the voltage output will be directly proportional to the strength of the magnetic field applied to the semiconductor sheet or 'active area'. A typical output produced by the Hall effect sensor used in this research is shown in Figure 1. The size of the active area is approximately one-fifth the size of the magnet being used in this experiment. This insures that the sensor is never operating in the fringe of the magnetic field which would cause an inaccurate reading.

Any magnet can be used with the Hall sensor. However, the best magnet for this application is one which can operate reliably within the ranges of the distances being measured. A magnet with a high residual induction will saturate the output of the sensor at or below a certain thickness, and will extend the upper operating range. A magnet with a lower residual induction will extend the lower sensing distance while the maximum upper distance will be contracted. A good magnet is also required to resist the tendency to demagnetize. Magnets with high coercive forces are essential when working in environments with strong demagnetizing fields, such as, near the rotors of alternating current motors.

The temperature coefficient of a magnet is a very important property. This coefficient indicates how much the strength of the magnet will change per degree of temperature change. Typical temperature coefficients of magnets range from -0.2% to -0.01% per degree Celsius. A low temperature coefficient is desired for this application due to the fact that the cure cycles result in very large temperature changes. These temperature changes force a resultant change in the output of the Hall sensor. Thus, the lower the temperature coefficient, the less change in the final output of the Hall sensor due to temperature.

2.2 Apparatus Description

The tooling required for testing the Hall sensor was made in-house out of aluminum. The tool plates dimensions were 10 x 12 x 0.375 inches. The

tool plate and caul plate (5 x 5 x 0.25 inches) were both machined in order to accommodate two ultrasonic transducers. One transducer (pulsar) was located above the laminate and the other (receiver) was located directly below the laminate and in line with the pulsar. The ultrasonic transducers were used to track the resin viscosity throughout the cure cycle [4]. The output of the ultrasound thus, provides additional insight into key points in the cure cycle where compaction proceeds most rapidly.

The Hall sensor currently used was built by Sprague Electronics [3] and has a maximum operating temperature of 125 °C, a sensitivity of 1.30 mV/Gauss(6mV/mil), and a sensing range of 0.25 inch. Because the Hall sensor is cooled (since curing temperatures are higher than its operating temperature), any direct contact with the curing composite would inhibit curing. The sensor thus had to be mounted away from the laminate. In doing so, the magnet also had to be remotely located. An extension arm was used to extend the magnet from the top of the laminate to a location directly above the 'active area' of the Hall sensor. Future applications of this sensor system will allow the magnet and sensor to be placed within the laminate. The sensor is not affected by nonferrous materials placed between it and the magnet.

2.3 Sensor Calibration

2.3.1 Compaction Effect

The Hall sensor was calibrated using vernier calipers accurate to 0.0005 inches. It was found that the calipers were ferrous and any direct attachment of the magnet to the calipers resulted in a magnetic circuit and altered the output of the sensor. This problem was circumvented by attaching two glass/epoxy extension arms to the calipers and then adhering the magnet and sensor to the ends of the arms away from any ferrous material.

Calibration of the sensor was accomplished by varying the distance between the extension arms and reading the voltage of the sensor output. All data was obtained using an IBM XT computer equipped with a Data Translation data acquisition board (Model 2805). The resulting data, collected at 25°C, were fit to the following polynomial:

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{thickness} \\ \text{(mils)} \end{array} = 4489.03 - 2912.17V + 674.28V^2 - 55.11V^3 \quad (1)$$

where, V is the output voltage of the Hall sensor in volts.

2.3.2 Temperature Effect

Several calibration runs were performed to find an empirical relationship between voltage change of the Hall sensor output and the temperature of the rare earth cobalt magnet. Having this relationship would allow the removal of the loss in strength of the magnet from the voltage/thickness relationship. These calibrations were made by placing the magnet above the sensor at a fixed distance using the extension arm. The apparatus was placed in the oven and heated to a temperature of 140°C while the output of the sensor was being measured. Fifty readings per channel were taken every ten seconds and the average of the fifty data points recorded.

The first data point collected was at room temperature and used as the reference. The reference voltage was subtracted from every voltage thereafter. Data from all calibrations runs were simply combined as shown in Figure 3 and fit to the following polynomial:

$$\Delta\text{VOLT (Volts)} = 9.02 \times 10^{-3} - 4.66 \times 10^{-4} \times \text{TEMPERATURE}(\text{°C}) \quad (2)$$

The literature value [5] given for the temperature dependence of an R.E. cobalt magnet is $0.05\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$ which agrees with the experimental value given above (0.0466%).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Cure Cycle Stages

An output for a monitored cure cycle is shown in Figure 4. The discontinuities in the ultrasonic output are due to changes in the gain setting made on-line to allow the output to remain in its linear range. The type of material used was a Hercules 3501-6 epoxy and a style 181 glass fabric. ten to fifteen ply panels were vacuum bagged and cured in an oven.

There are four distinct areas marked on Figure 4. Zone A represents vacuum compaction prior to heating of the oven. This zone shows a very high rate of compaction and appears to last approximately five minutes. The times mentioned here are purely for reference and do not indicate that in all test cases the zone divisions occur at the given times.

Zone B, which extends from five minutes to fifteen minutes, shows continued compaction. The rate of compaction in zone B is lower than in zone A. The compaction in this area is influenced by the resin softening because of rise in temperature.

Zone C extends from fifteen to forty minutes. Initially, the random variation in thickness indicated by the sensor was thought to be caused by the flow of resin and volatiles out of the material. Upon closer inspection however, this was found not to be the case. An unexpected problem (discussed below) regarding the experimental apparatus seems to be the cause of the thickness fluctuation.

In zone D, compaction rate tends to zero as the viscosity increases rapidly. Any additional thickness change is due to contraction as a result of polymerization or thermal effects. At this point in the cure cycle, the thickness can no longer be manipulated by the application of pressure.

3.2 Flotation Problem

The use of ultrasound during this research proved to be very helpful in pinpointing the cause of thickness fluctuations. As seen in Figure 4, zone C approximately begins at the point where ultrasound indicates minimum resin viscosity. In addition, zone C ends soon after the viscosity starts increasing. The reason for the random variation in the thickness of the laminate in zone C is thought to be caused by a y-axis instability problem in the apparatus setup. The axis perpendicular to the sensor and parallel to the tooling plate is defined as the y-axis. Any variation in the thickness of the laminate in the y-direction causes movement of the magnet, located at the end of the extension arm. The greater the variation in thickness in the y-direction the larger the error in the sensor's output.

3.3 Sensor Accuracy

The results presented in Figure 5 and Table 1 show the actual thickness of the laminate after the cure cycle and the thickness indicated by the

sensor. Good agreement between actual and measured panel thickness is evident with the percent error ranging from zero to 8.4%. The greatest error occurred during a test in which a temporary bag leak caused loss of vacuum. By monitoring thickness data vacuum failure and bag leaks can be detected by noticing rapid increases of thickness.

A simple least squares analysis was performed on the polynomials (Equations 1 and 2) and 95% simultaneous prediction intervals were obtained. The results show an approximate accuracy of ± 0.003 inches over the range of 0.090 to 0.250 inches. A detailed description of these calculations is presented elsewhere [1].

Because only one sensor was used the variation in the laminate thickness could not be corrected for on-line. Furthermore, due to the fact that sensors will in the future be placed directly below the magnet, the y-instability of the magnet should not be a factor in applications of this sensor system.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A compaction and thickness sensor has been developed and is operational. The sensor has been calibrated for thickness and temperature effects and calibration confidence intervals have been established. The sensor can measure in-situ the thickness of composite materials during the cure phase with an approximate accuracy of ± 0.003 inches over the range of 0.090 to 0.250 inches.

Furthermore, it has been shown that the sensor can be used to detect bag leaks and seal-offs by detecting a sharp increase in thickness in the affected area. The results of this research show that the Hall effect sensor can successfully be used for on-line monitoring of the thickness of a curing composite.

5. REFERENCES

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6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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7. BIOGRAPHY

Dean R. Hofmann received a bachelor of chemical engineering in 1988 and a M.S. in materials engineering in 1990 from the University of Dayton. He has done extensive research and development of advanced composite materials for various aerospace applications. His area of expertise also includes in-situ sensor development and intelligent control of composite materials manufacturing

Tony E. Saliba is an associate professor of chemical and materials engineering at the University of Dayton. He has over 35 publications in the area of process modeling and traditional and expert system control of advanced composite materials. He is the co-designer of the first curriculum of a bachelor degree in composite materials engineering at Winona State University. He is a senior midwest national director and chairperson of the College Composite Curriculum Committee for the Society for the Advancement of Material and Process Engineering (SAMPE).

Figure 1: Typical Hall Effect Voltage Change with Thickness

SENSOR MOUNTING BLOCK

SIDE VIEW

Figure 2: Three dimensional view of experimental setup.

Figure 3: Calibration Curve

Figure 4: Sample Output

Figure 5: Graphical Display of Results.

Table 1: Measured and Actual Panel Thicknesses

Test #	Sensor(mils)	Actual(mils)	%Error
1	162	162	0
2	163	161	1.3
3	162	155	4.5
4	181	167	8.4
5	113	107	5.6
6	161	158	1.9

